

Effect of penicillin on nucleic acid^a and protein content^b and enzyme activity of rice seedlings. Calcutta, India.

Treatment	Embryo of 5-day-old seedlings			Endosperm (3 days after germination)				
	DNA	RNA	Protein	DNA	RNA	Protein	α -amylase ^c	RNase ^d
Control	16	58	3.5	23	91	3.1	3.4	0.40
Penicillin (ppm)								
500	25	101	4.5	33	127	4.0	4.6	1.96
1,000	30	110	4.9	31	122	3.5	4.6	1.30

^aDNA and RNA are in $\mu\text{g}/100$ mg fresh wt. ^bProtein is in $\text{mg}/100$ mg fresh wt. ^cAs mg maltose released per 10 endosperms and 10 minutes. ^dAbsorbancy at 260 nm per 10 endosperms and 30 minutes.

seedlings increased progressively when GA₃ was combined with increasing concentrations of penicillin. The interaction

was additive. Penicillin probably stimulated elongation in a manner similar to GA₃. ■

Elongation of second leaf sheath of TN1 rice seedlings. 1 = control (water); 2, 3, 4 = 100, 500, and 1,000 ppm penicillin, respectively; 5 = GA₃ (10^{-5} M); 6 = GA₃ + 100 ppm penicillin; 7 = GA₃ + 500 ppm penicillin; 8 = GA₃ + 1,000 ppm penicillin.

Aeroponic technique for root system studies of rice *Oryza sativa* L.

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In studies of the relationship of rice root systems to drought resistance at IRRI since 1970, roots have been grown in soil-filled mylar tubes, root boxes, and in the field. These methods and attendant sampling problems are laborious and time-consuming, and damage to roots can occur during sampling of large populations. The need to study a rice root system with its components intact led to the development of an aeroponic culture system. A nutrient solution is pumped from a reservoir through an atomizing mist nozzle at the base of a cylindrical drum (see figure) about 90 cm in diameter. The nutrient solution mist continuously bathes rice roots hanging from the cylinder top. Excess nutrient solution drains back into the reservoir for reuse. The cylinder is covered with a plywood top in which plants are grown in Styrofoam plant holders. Holes 5.0 cm in diameter spaced 7.5 cm centers allow the plants to grow competitively without entangling their roots. Each plant holder is 5.0 cm in diameter with a 2.1 cm center hole. The bottom of each holder is wrapped with plastic screen held securely by a rubber band.

To produce good quality seedlings for

General view of the aeroponic device inside a phytotron glasshouse at IRRI.

use in the aeroponic system, rice seeds were pretreated with 0.2% mercuric chloride to prevent fungus growth and Pregerminated in petri dishes. After two days they were transferred to plastic sieves in a plastic tray containing just enough 50% concentration nutrient solution to cover the germinating seeds. After 11 days, seedlings were transplanted into Styrofoam plant holders inside the phytotron working area. Roots were sprayed with demineralized water to prevent dehydration during transplanting.

Immediately after seedlings were transferred to the drum cover, it was set on top of the drum, the aeroponic system switched on, and the seedlings

began to receive a mist of standard nutrient solution. The pH was adjusted to 5.0 before the solution was added to the aeroponic reservoir and readjusted daily to avoid nutrient imbalance. The culture solution was renewed weekly from transplanting to sampling.

During the first week after transplanting, only a 50% concentration of the prepared culture solution was used. Beginning from the second week, a full concentration was used. Nitrogen was increased from 40 to 80 ppm the fourth week.

Aeroponic chambers can be operated in a series by extending the air and nutrient solution pressure systems serving the units. ■